

German Marine Seismic Data Access

Janine Berndt¹, Christian Hübscher², Hanno Keil³, Andreas Lehmann¹, and Christian Berndt¹

¹GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel, Germany

²University of Hamburg, Germany

³University of Bremen, Germany

28/04/2023

This work has been funded by the German Research Foundation (NFDI₄Earth, DFG project no. 460036893, <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/>).

Pilot title	German Marine Seismic Data Access
Project Duration	March 2022 - February 2023
Contributors¹	Janine Berndt (Investigation, Conceptualization, Data curation), Christian Berndt (Supervision, Conceptualization), Maximilian Betz (Resources), Daniel Damaske (Data curation), Janine Felden (Resources), Christian Hübscher (Resources), Hanno Keil (Resources), Sebastian Krastel (Resources), Andreas Lehmann (Resources), Hela Mehrstens (Resources), Cord Papenberg (Data curation), Carsten Schirnack (Conceptualization), Mechita Schmidt-Aursch (Resources), Michael Schnabel (Data curation, Resources), Estella Weigelt (Data curation, Resources), Gauvain Wiemer (Conceptualization)
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.7875451
Corresponding author	Janine Berndt, jberndt@geomar.de

Abstract

Reflection seismic data are the prime source of information for the subsurface structure as they provide the highest resolution of any geophysical technique. As such they have been used for a large variety of academic and commercial purposes. For many decades reflection seismic data were the largest data sets in Earth sciences, which created significant storage and archival problems and until today there is no international, European, or German data portal that is used throughout the community. Within this pilot project, we have started to develop a unifying data infrastructure, to kick off data archeology for

¹ Based on the CRediT Contributor Roles Taxonomy: <https://credit.niso.org/>

existing data, and to prepare for future archival of reflection seismic data from future research cruises. The initiative serves primarily Germany's marine geophysics community as represented by the working group Marine Geophysics AGMAR, but it is closely aligned with similar initiatives in the U.S. and Italy. The pilot for reflection seismic data contributes to the efforts of NFDI4Earth to establish a distributed infrastructure for data curation by harmonized data workflows with connections to international data repositories.

I. Introduction

Reflection seismic data are the prime source of information on the subsurface as they allow imaging at very high spatial and temporal resolution. They have been acquired for the past 60 years for various scientific and economic purposes. In particular, their usefulness in the identification of hydrocarbon reservoirs led to an explosion in seismic activity since the 1970s.

Seismic data volumes are fairly large, i.e. 100s of MB to several TB for individual surveys, which posed challenges in data management in the past when computers were less powerful and data storage precious. Also, the wide diversity in the acquisition systems and the processing of these data meant that it is difficult to agree on common metadata dictionaries and a consistent description of the seismic data.

The NFDI4Earth Pilot **German Marine Seismic Data Access** is an initiative by the working group Marine Geophysics AGMAR of the FKPE (Forschungskollegium Physik des Erdkörpers). The two main task areas were to establish an agreed standard for data archival and to develop a rescue strategy for legacy seismic data for the foreseeable future.

II. Results

II.1. Access to existing seismic data

The first objective of the pilot study was to develop a strategy for marine seismic data archeology to make existing data accessible for posterity. This part of the project has progressed fairly slowly despite support and plenty of goodwill from the actors. Within several meetings, the status quo was investigated and compiled. A summary of the situation is given below.

GEOMAR stores all multi-channel seismic data that have been handled since 2000 on disk robots. These data can fairly easily be made accessible through data portals. In addition, there are about 10.000 9" track tapes. Within the pilot project, we handled about 80 % of these tapes to check their contents. Transfer of their content to a hard disk requires a subcontractor as the retrieval

is technically challenging. The tapes contain a variety of geophysical data, including unique raw data from areas to which nobody will have access in the foreseeable future due to political reasons or environmental restrictions. In addition, GEOMAR data management has purchased several different tape reading devices to transfer data from DAT tapes to the disk robot.

The University of Kiel has stored its seismic data on a NAS server for the last 11 years. In addition, numerous DAT tapes with data collected by former employees are awaiting transfer to a hard disk. A list of the data in question has already been compiled.

The situation at the University of Hamburg is similar to the University of Kiel. The data for the last 10 to 15 years can be found in digital form on hard disk, and some of the older data are still on DAT tapes. Zipped data are archived at Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum (DKRZ).

The University of Bremen has its data archived at the institute. Moreover, a list of all cruises conducted since 1991 can be found online <https://www.mtu.uni-bremen.de/cruises.html>.

Alfred Wegener Institute Bremerhaven has all its data already stored in-house and is in the process of archiving its processed 2D seismic data according to an in-house standard set by Estella Weigelt in PANGAEA. Track data are visualized on the maps@awi portal and can be found under the keyword "seismic" on the website <https://maps.awi.de/awimaps/catalog/>.

Bundesanstalt für Geowissenschaften und Rohstoffe (BGR) has all its data (back to 1974) already archived in its internal repository and visualizes its data tracks on the SeaDataNet portal. This archive covers about 350.000 km of seismic profiles. More information can be found on their website <https://geoportal.bgr.de/mapapps/resources/apps/geoportal/index.html?lang=en - />.

This shows that there is a wide variety of solutions and that the state of data management is highly variable. Also, it is clear that retrieval and publication of the existing data require significant resources.

a) Implemented Solution

The objective of the pilot study was not to develop a solution for the retrieval and publication of all the existing marine seismic data at German institutions as this requires resources far beyond the possibilities of NFDI4Earth. Instead, this part of the pilot study aimed to make progress toward a common retrieval and publication strategy.

The first step towards a solution was to investigate how other international players are dealing with this problem. This can be divided into academic initiatives, governmental initiatives, and industry initiatives.

A good example of academic initiatives is MGDS (<https://www.marine-geo.org/index.php>). This U.S. initiative has curated most of the academic U.S. American reflection seismic data to make them available under FAIR principles. While the interoperability is limited, the data are at least findable and accessible to a large extent. Also, the data come with a rudimentary data processing description. This initiative could serve as an example for future data management of the German seismic data for example within DAM through PANGAEA. Subject to funding we propose to follow the example of MGDS and store both the raw data and processed seismic data in PANGAEA and make them available through the DAM portal *marine-data.de*. As most legacy data will not come with complete metadata descriptions, the aim must be to provide these as completely as possible. For the raw data, we propose to use the same data standard as developed during the pilot project, and for the processed data the metadata has to be flexible. If at all possible, the processed data should be linked back to the raw data entries as this would allow reprocessing the data and make the results reproducible.

A good example of government data initiatives is the North Sea Transition Authority portal that endeavors to make accessible all seismic data in the U.K. exclusive economic zone. A prime example of industry data management initiatives is the Norwegian consortium *disco2* which curates all seismic data for the Norwegian exclusive economic zone. All data are online accessible with full data descriptions and processing histories and in different formats. This database holds about 14 petabytes of reflection seismic data. The system is governed by the Norwegian Petroleum Directorate but implemented commercially through a contractor company (CGG) and usage is not free.

Another data management initiative is Open Subsurface Data Universe (OSDU) which combines the data management efforts of many industry and academic institutions to standardize data management efforts and make the data interoperable. Within the NFDI4Earth pilot project, GEOMAR joined OSDU to ascertain that standards developed by this international consortium are incorporated into German seismic data management efforts.

We have aligned the activities in the NFDI4Earth pilot closely with the data management efforts within the Deutsche Allianz Meeresforschung (DAM) in which all institutions that collect academic seismic data are members. As a result, it is possible to continue the work of the pilot project for another three years and flag the need for further resources to the funding agencies. Also, we have received indications that we will receive funding for copying the 9" tape reels at GEOMAR to hard disk.

Finally, we have tried to raise funding for the implementation of the data retrieval and archival strategy through two proposals. Along with AWI (Janine Felden), we have submitted a proposal to the Helmholtz metadata initiative (HMC) which was unfortunately not successful. Recently, we

submitted a Horizon Europe proposal with a set of international partners which is still in review. It is clear that the retrieval of the existing reflection seismic data in all institutions requires significant funding (between 1.5 and 2 million EUR over 5 years) which has to be secured before the roadmap can be implemented.

b) Data and software availability

This does not apply to this part of the project.

c) Innovation and FAIRness

FAIR access to the existing seismic data can be implemented with the necessary resources. While the raw data management is straightforward and has been successfully implemented elsewhere, e.g. at MGDS, the archival of processed seismic data is difficult to standardize. Within OSDU, there are efforts in this direction but full reaching full interoperability for example for machine learning is not straightforward. Within the proposed Horizon Europe project FAIRS-X, we will investigate to what extent processed data have to be harmonized and described to make them available for machine learning.

II.2. Workflows for future seismic data

Within the NFDI4Earth pilot study, we have developed a metadata standard for newly acquired reflection seismic data. This metadata standard has been developed in collaboration with the users and checked against the common practice at different institutions, e.g. Bundesanstalt für Geowissenschaften und Rohstoffe, or Lamont Doherty Earth Observatory as well as through consultation with expert users. These consultations resulted in a minimum list of metadata that can easily be collected and are sufficient to fully describe the newly acquired data ensuring reproducibility, findability, availability, interoperability, and reusability. However, this basic standard is still under development and we hope to finalize a metadata standard for raw seismic data on the RV Sonne Cruise SO299-2 in August 2023 while implementing SOPs for future cruises for GEOMAR and the University of Kiel. For the other institutes and universities, we have to conduct test cruises as each institute and each university has a different acquisition setup and therefore acquires different data output which needs to be reflected and implemented in the metadata standard.

a) Implemented Solution

The solution that we have tested during cruises SO294, MSM113, and, TAN2305 is based on minimum specifications that can be visualized in the following conceptual database design. The advantage of this simple set of metadata is that they are easy to implement, ensuring take up in the community. During the design phase, we realized that it would be possible to introduce more comprehensive data models that would allow a link with the logistics database through PIDs for

each of the used air guns and streamer segments. While this would allow efficient workflows at GEOMAR by laser scanning equipment to compile the metadata, this would be at the expense of universal applicability and slow down the take-up of the concept.

Figure 1 Conceptual database model for the raw seismic data. The concept involves the calculation of metadata for each seismic shot resulting in one complete metadata ASCII file for each SEG-D seismic data file.

With help from the DAM data management, PANGAEA, and the Leitstelle Deutsche Forschungsschiffe, it was possible to not only test the solution during two German cruises. In addition, and beyond the original plans for the pilot project, we were able to test if the data can be automatically transferred via mass data management (MDM). This system is routinely used to transfer the ship-board data such as navigation and meteorology data from the ship to PANGAEA. This workflow is still being tested, but will ultimately make the data management of the raw data transparent for the user.

b) Data and Software Availability

The seismic raw data will be uploaded to the PANGAEA repository immediately after the expeditions and the data will be findable through the portal *marine-data.de*. Routinely, the data will be under a two-year plus two-year moratorium (This only applies to seismic data!) before they are freely available. This moratorium can be further extended within reasonable limits, e.g. for the duration of cruise-associated Ph.D. theses to ensure the acceptability of the concept in the community. The standardized data format ensures interoperability.

All scripts to generate the metadata (csh and Python) will be publicly available with the publication of the standard operating procedure once the uploads to PANGAEA have been tested later this year.

c) Innovation and FAIRness

The pilot study has produced for the first time a marine seismic data management concept that can be used by all German marine geophysics departments and allows them to fulfill their DFG obligations for the use of ship time. The standardization of the metadata ensures interoperability and access to the raw data for example for machine learning.

The implementation through the mass data management (MDM) that is operated by the research vessels ensures a high degree of reliability and user-friendliness that should ensure the uptake of the concept by all marine geophysics groups in Germany. While this is not applicable for Germany-led cruises on foreign vessels the system is versatile enough that the metadata can be generated in the same way and the data can easily be uploaded to PANGAEA and *marine-data.de* after the cruise.

III. Challenges and Gaps

The first objective to develop a strategy for retrieving and publishing existing marine seismic data in Germany has partly been achieved. It is now clear how much resources it would require to implement the strategy, i.e. 1 full-time position at each of the partner institutions for between 3 and 5 years and approximately 200k EUR funding for copying existing 9" tape reels to hard disks. This is substantial and cannot be covered by the involved institutions. Given the value of the existing data that have partly been acquired in areas that are not accessible anymore, it would be a very good value for money for the funding agencies to invest in the rescue of these data and this is our prime recommendation. There are two main challenges. The first challenge pertains to the volume of data that had been underestimated at the outset of the project, leading to delays in the schedule. The second challenge is the complete description of processed seismic data. It is in the nature of the discipline that a complete, reproducible metadata description of processed data is not possible (e.g. due to information loss due to migration or stacking). Thus, it is necessary to come up with workable solutions that find a good compromise between the superior reusability and accessibility of processed seismic data and complete reproducibility. We propose to achieve this by fairly complete metadata descriptions of the processed seismic data accepting that there are gaps for example caused by proprietary migration algorithms on one hand and linkage back to the raw data which should enable future scientists to reproduce the results on the other hand. It is certainly necessary to strengthen the links to international

initiatives such as OSDU to ascertain that the metadata descriptions for the processed seismic data are as consistent and compatible as possible.

IV. Relevance for the community and NFDI4Earth

The pilot study has provided the crucial impetus for the marine geophysics community to start working together on reflection seismic data archival. Until this project data management was different not only for each institute but for each cruise. The project provides a blueprint for how the raw data can be transferred directly to PANGAEA and made findable through the portal *marine-data.de*. Beyond the expectations raised in the proposal, we managed to agree on a data standard and were able to test it not only on one cruise but on three cruises including one on a foreign vessel. This provided valuable insight and allowed us to spot inaccuracies and incomplete descriptions of the metadata standard, which will be incorporated in the final standard operating procedure that is due to be published later in 2023 when loading and publication of the data have been tested in PANGAEA and *marine-data.de*, respectively.

Figure 2 Framework of the different parties involved in this pilot.

The project provided significant links between the marine geophysics community (AGMAR) and the data management community, e.g. in DAM (*marine-data.de*), PANGAEA (NFDI4Earth Repository), and GEOMAR (NFDI4Earth User Support Network) that were non-existent or weak beforehand.

V. Future Directions

The German seismic community will further develop the standard for raw 2D seismic data and fully implement a final standard in the DAM underway data management cycle to ensure storage and visibility of all data acquired in the near future on German research vessels. However, it will be necessary to issue different SOPs (Standard Operating Procedures) for each institute and university to reflect their different recording systems and requirements to obtain metadata according to the common metadata standard for 2D multichannel seismic data. GEOMAR already has a cruise dedicated (SO299-2) to finally implement a revised and improved metadata standard via Python scripts/Jupyter notebooks. The other institutes will follow shortly and manpower permitting. Furthermore, we will try to retrieve as much legacy data as possible depending on the necessary funding provided. It is planned to archive these legacy data at the German repository PANGAEA and make their tracks visible on the portal *marine-data.de*.

In addition, we will develop and propose a metadata standard for 3D multichannel seismic and active OBS (Ocean Bottom Seismometer) soon depending on funding to ensure the full implementation of the FAIR standard to all different seismic data.

The German seismic community has already reached out to other leading European stakeholders to develop a joint metadata standard. This would lead to a more efficient approach to managing data sets and their interoperability enabling optimization of the interactions between stakeholders, industry, and science partnerships and contributing to EU data strategy goals. The ultimate goal is to foster the European market for data space sharing and collaboration to enhance joint business models through a higher degree of interoperability, increased data availability, and easier data exchange both for the scientific communities and the industry.